

AI-Assisted Optical Imaging for Intraoperative Tumor Margin Assessment in Solid Tumor Surgery: A Systematic Review

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Introduction

Accurate intraoperative tumor margin assessment remains a major challenge in solid tumor surgery, as positive margins are associated with increased local recurrence, reoperation, and need for adjuvant treatment. Conventional methods, including visual inspection and frozen section analysis, are limited by sampling error, time requirements, and variable diagnostic performance. Optical imaging integrated with artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a promising approach for real-time tumor delineation. This systematic review evaluates the diagnostic performance and clinical utility of AI-assisted optical imaging for intraoperative tumor margin assessment.

Materials and Methods

A systematic search of PubMed, Embase, Scopus, and Web of Science was conducted in accordance with PRISMA 2020 guidelines. Studies published between 2021 and 2026 were screened using predefined criteria. Eligible studies were original human investigations evaluating AI-assisted optical imaging for intraoperative tumor margin assessment in solid tumors and reporting diagnostic performance metrics (sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, or AUC). Reviews, meta-analyses, editorials, conference abstracts without extractable data, and animal studies were excluded. Methodological quality was assessed using QUADAS-2.

Results

A total of 44 studies were included, reflecting increasing interest in AI-assisted optical imaging. The most frequently evaluated modalities were fluorescence-guided imaging, hyperspectral imaging, Raman spectroscopy, and optical coherence tomography (OCT). Among included studies, diagnostic performance was generally favorable but heterogeneous across tumor types and platforms. Reported accuracy ranged from 54–100% for Raman spectroscopy, 69–99% for hyperspectral imaging, and 82–99% for OCT. Prior pooled analyses in head and neck surgery reported sensitivity/specificity of 95.7%/82.7% for tumor-targeted fluorescence and 91.9%/85.5% for optical techniques. Overall, AI-assisted optical imaging may improve real-time intraoperative margin assessment, although variability and limited external validation restrict comparability.

Conclusion

AI-assisted optical imaging is a promising adjunct for intraoperative tumor margin assessment. However, current evidence remains heterogeneous, with limited external validation and lack of standardized prospective studies. Larger multicenter investigations are required before routine clinical implementation.

Keywords

Artificial intelligence; Optical imaging; Intraoperative imaging; Tumor margin assessment; Surgical oncology; Fluorescence-guided imaging; Hyperspectral imaging; Raman spectroscopy; Optical coherence tomography